

STACKING SEQUENCE EFFECTS IN OVER-HEIGHT COMPACT TENSION TESTS OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Stacking sequence effects are important in tensile strength of notched composite laminates. Hallett and Wisnom [1] and Hallett et al. [2, 3] studied stacking sequence effects on tensile strength of notched composite laminates. Laffan et al. [4] also studied layup effects on standard compact tension specimens and their fracture toughness.

The Over-height Compact Tension (OCT) test was developed by Kongshavn and Poursartip [5] to determine fracture properties of composite laminates. Damage development in OCT tests was investigated by Floyd [6], and Williams et al. [7]. Li et al. [8] carried out experimental investigations into quasi-isotropic OCT specimens with surface 45 degree plies. The damage progress was studied by using X-rays and fracture toughness for failure initiation was calculated. To apply the Digital Image Correlation technique (DIC), Zobeiry [9] tested quasi-isotropic OCT specimens with surface 90 degree plies to minimize the surface damage. Fracture toughness for failure propagation was calculated from the fracture process zone measurements from DIC. However, no studies have been done to compare the different layups used by Li et al. [8] and Zobeiry [9].

In the present paper, quasi-isotropic OCT specimens with different stacking sequences were tested. Specimens which have single ply thicknesses are called dispersed-ply laminates. Other specimens in which two plies of the same orientation are placed together in the layup are referred to as blocked-ply laminates. Dispersed-ply laminates and blocked-ply laminates were compared. In addition, specimens with surface 45 degree plies which have a double 0 degree ply on the mid-plane (effectively a double thickness ply) were compared to the ones with surface 90 degree plies which only have single 0 degree plies throughout. A Finite Element (FE) method using the explicit code LS-Dyna with

interface elements to model splitting and delamination was used to better understand the damage pattern [10].

2 Experimental Studies

2.1 Test Setup

The OCT specimens with dimensions shown in Fig. 1 were tested in an Instron 100 kN test machine under displacement control at a rate of 1 mm/min. The Pin Opening Displacement (POD) was measured by an Instron extensometer with a 10mm gauge length and ± 5 mm travel distance. A pair of anti-buckling bars was attached to the back faces of each OCT specimen to prevent any buckling failure.

All the tests were monitored by a DIC system which contained Prosilica GE cameras with Rodenstock 60 mm f/4 Rodagon Enlarging Lenses as shown in Fig. 2. Correlated Solutions' Vic-Snap 2010 and Vic-3D 2010 software was used for post processing.

Interrupted tests in which the specimens were unloaded after the first observed load drop and the first major load drop (over 5%) on the respective load-POD curve were carried out to study the failure mechanisms via X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) scanning.

The material used was Hexcel's HexPly® IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy pre-preg with a 0.125mm nominal ply thickness. The blocked-ply laminates in which two plies of the same orientation are placed together in the layup effectively have a 0.25mm ply thickness. The schematics of the typical layups tested are illustrated in Fig. 3. Blocked-ply laminates tested were $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_{2s}$ and $[90_2/45_2/0_2/-45_2]_{2s}$ laminates. Dispersed-ply $[45/90/-45/0]_{4s}$ laminates were also tested to compare with $[90/45/0/-45]_{4s}$ laminates investigated by Zobeiry [9].

2.2 Experimental Results

During all the OCT tests, fracture in front of the notch occurred together with load drops on the load-POD curves. All specimens suffered compressive failure at their back faces in the final stage of the tests. Experimental load-POD curves are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

The failure initiation loads and peak loads are higher in the specimens with blocked plies than with dispersed plies.

With dispersed plies, the load-POD curves of different layups are very similar including the average failure initiation loads and peak loads. For blocked plies with surface 45 degree plies, the average failure initiation load is higher than that for blocked plies with surface 90 degree plies.

3 Numerical Studies

An FE method using the explicit code LS-Dyna with interface elements to model splits and delaminations was applied.

In the present FE analysis, splitting elements were pre-defined along multiple paths within all plies, and delamination elements were pre-defined between all plies with different fibre orientations. In Fig. 6, the lines represent the potential splits, and a schematic shows how the cohesive interface elements are connected. The properties of the cohesive interface elements are listed in Table 1. The lamina properties are listed in Table 2. The mixed-mode traction-displacement relationship of the cohesive interface elements is illustrated in Fig. 7.

A criterion based on Weibull theory has been used to predict fibre failure. Weibull theory supposes that the strength of a brittle-like material is controlled by flaws which follow a Weibull distribution [10].

4 Results Analysis

4.1 Test Results Analysis

By checking the CT images from interrupted tests in Figs. 8 to 13, the damage zone in the 0 degree plies (or ply blocks) in the laminates with different layups after fibre breakage was compared.

Comparing Fig. 8 against Fig. 9, and Fig. 11 against Fig. 12, the split length and delamination area are found to be bigger in the 0 degree plies with blocked plies than with dispersed plies due to more energy being available. Such sub-critical damage can blunt the stress concentration and account for the higher failure initiation loads and peak loads in the laminates with blocked plies.

In Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, the damage ahead of the notch was examined after the tests were stopped following the first observed load drop to study the failure initiation. Local fibre failure was found in the 0 degree plies. In both dispersed-ply and blocked-ply laminates with surface 45 degree plies, the splits in the central double 0 degree ply (or ply block) are longer than those in the outboard single 0 degree plies (or ply blocks). In Fig. 9(a) the split is long enough to blunt the stress concentration and retard any fibre failure in the central 0 degree ply block in the blocked-ply laminates with surface 45 degree plies. By comparison, in the blocked-ply laminates with surface 90 degree plies, the damage zone in all the single 0 degree ply blocks as shown in Fig. 10 is similar to that in the outboard single 0 degree ply blocks but much smaller than the central double 0 degree ply block in the blocked-ply laminates with surface 45 degree plies. This may give rise to higher initiation loads in the laminates with blocked plies with surface 45 degree plies than with surface 90 degree plies. However, this effect is not significant enough to cause any obvious difference in the laminates with dispersed plies.

In Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, the damage ahead of the notch was examined after the tests were stopped following the first major load drop (over 5%) to study the failure propagation before final failure. In both dispersed-ply and blocked-ply laminates with surface 45 degree plies, the damage zone in the central double 0 degree ply (or ply block) is bigger than that in the outboard single 0 degree plies (or ply blocks). Delaminations dominate the major load drops of the blocked-ply laminates. Furthermore, the damage zone in the central double 0 degree ply block reaches the edge of the specimen with blocked-ply laminates with surface 45 degree plies. By comparison, in the blocked-ply laminates with surface 90 degree plies as shown in Fig. 13, the damage zone in all the single 0 degree ply blocks is similar to that in the outboard single 0 degree ply blocks in the blocked-ply laminates with surface 45 degree plies.

4.2 FE Results Analysis

By checking the damage pattern from the FE results in Figs. 14 to 19, the damage in the 0 degree plies before the Weibull criterion is met was compared in the models with different layups.

Comparing Fig. 14 against Fig. 17, Fig. 15 against Fig. 18, and Fig. 16 against Fig. 19, the 0 degree splits are longer in the models with blocked plies

than with dispersed plies due to more energy being available. Such different split lengths can blunt the stress concentration at the notch tip, and account for the higher failure initiation load in the laminates with blocked plies than the dispersed-ply laminates.

In the models of blocked-ply laminates with surface 45 degree plies, the splits in the central double 0 degree ply block are longer than those in the outboard single 0 degree ply blocks before the Weibull criterion is met. By comparison, in the laminates with surface 90 degree plies as shown in Fig. 19, the split length in the single 0 degree ply block is similar to that in the outboard single 0 degree plies in the laminates with surface 45 degree plies because they are all of the same ply thickness. This may give rise to higher initiation loads in the laminates with blocked plies with surface 45 degree plies than with surface 90 degree plies.

5 Summary

The stacking sequence is an important factor in notched tensile strength. Firstly, blocked-ply OCT specimens are stronger than dispersed-ply OCT specimens due to longer splits and bigger delamination area blunting the stress concentration at the notch tip. Secondly, the failure initiation in specimens with blocked plies with surface 45 degree plies occurs at a higher load level than those with blocked plies with surface 90 degree plies due to its central double 0 degree ply block. Lastly, such different 0 degree split lengths with different layups are less significant in notched tensile strength of specimens with dispersed plies.

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Fig. 1. OCT specimen dimensions [8]

Fig. 2. Test setup

Fig. 5. Load-POD curves for blocked plies

Fig. 3. Stacking sequences

Fig. 4. Load-POD curves for dispersed plies

Lines show pre-defined splitting paths

Fig. 6. Pre-defined interface elements

Fig. 7. Mixed-mode traction displacement relationship for interface elements [11]

(a) Central double 0 degree ply

(b) Outboard single 0 degree ply block (2 plies)

Fig. 9. CT images of $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_{2s}$ blocked-ply laminates after the first observed load drop at 14.6 kN

(b) Outboard single 0 degree ply

Fig. 8. CT images of $[45/90/-45/0]_{4s}$ dispersed-ply laminates after the first observed load drop at 9.9 kN

Fig. 10. CT images of 0 degree ply block (2 plies) in $[90_2/45_2/0_2/-45_2]_{2s}$ blocked-ply laminates after the first observed load drop at 11.6 kN

(a) Central double 0 degree ply block (4 plies)

(a) Central double 0 degree ply

(b) Outboard single double 0 degree ply

Fig. 11. CT images of $[45/90/-45/0]_{4s}$ dispersed-ply laminates after the major load drop at 11.2 kN

(a) Central double 0 degree ply block (4 plies)

(b) Single double 0 degree ply block (2 plies)

Fig. 12. CT images of $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_{2s}$ blocked-ply laminates after the major load drop at 22.4 kN

Fig. 13. CT images of 0 degree ply block (2 plies) in $[90_2/45_2/0_2/-45_2]_{2s}$ blocked-ply laminates after the major load drop at 20.6 kN

Fig. 14. Splits in the central double 0 degree ply in $[45/90/-45/0]_{4s}$ dispersed-ply laminates at 7.7 kN (1.5 mm-long)

Fig. 16. Splits in the single 0 degree ply in $[90/45/0/-45]_{4s}$ dispersed-ply laminates at 7.7 kN (0.9 mm-long)

Fig. 15. Splits in the outboard single 0 degree ply in $[45/90/-45/0]_{4s}$ dispersed-ply laminates at 7.7 kN (1.0 mm-long)

Fig. 17. Splits in the central double 0 degree ply block (4 plies) in $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_{2s}$ blocked-ply laminates at 12.0 kN (10.8 mm-long)

Fig. 18. Splits in the outboard single 0 degree ply block (2 plies) in $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_{2s}$ blocked-ply laminates at 12.0 kN (7.6 mm-long)

Fig. 19. Splits in the single 0 degree ply block (2 plies) in $[90_2/45_2/0_2/-45_2]_{2s}$ blocked-ply laminates at 12.0 kN (7.0 mm-long)

G_{IC} (N/mm)	G_{IIC} (N/mm)	σ_1^{\max} (MPa)	σ_{II}^{\max} (MPa)	α
0.2	1.0	60	90	1.0

Table 1. Cohesive interface element properties of IM7/8552 [2]

E_{11} (GPa)	$E_{22}=E_{33}$ (GPa)	$G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	m
161	11.4	5.17	3.98	41
σ_{11t}^{\max} (MPa)	$\alpha_{22}=\alpha_{33}$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	α_{11} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	ν_{23}
3131*	3×10^{-5}	0.0	0.320	0.436

* 3131 MPa is for unit volume material.

Table 2. Lamina properties of IM7/8552 [2][12]